

ORIGIN OF FOOTBALL ENGLISH

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Abstract: *General-purpose dictionaries may be assumed to reflect the core vocabulary of current language use. This implies that subsequent editions of a desk dictionary should mirror lexical changes in the general language. These include cases where special-language words have become so familiar to the general public that they may also be regarded as part of general language. This is the perspective of the present study on English football vocabulary.*

Keywords: *football language, diachronic perspective, general-purpose dictionaries, learners' dictionaries, lexical change*

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, the relationship between English football language and general language over time, with special regard to vocabulary, is our main focus. Such a diachronic perspective also involves change within football vocabulary, mainly an incremental process – for example, the word striker was introduced in the 1960s – although leaving in its wake a fair number of more or less obsolete expressions; for instance, the term center half (along with left-half and right-half) started to disappear in the latter half of the 20th century following the emergence of new tactical formations. [1]

BACKGROUND

Football, as a popular pastime in some form or other, has been around for ages. [2] One indication of this, on British soil, is that, according to the Oxford English Dictionary (OED), the first occurrence of the word football dates back to the Middle Ages (1409). Football is also referred to by Shakespeare, in *The Comedy of Errors* and *King Lear*, in a way implying that, in those early days, football's reputation was at a constant low, owing to its extremely rough and violent nature, occasionally resulting in fatal casualties.¹ Football at that time could certainly be called “the people's game”, although in a different sense from now, when the world's most popular sport is also commonly referred to as “the beautiful game”. Thus the historical trajectory of football can, in several respects, be considered a true from-rags-to-riches tale. [3]

In contrast to the long and winding road of football, football language cannot boast a very long history, the modern game being invented, i.e. regulated, in Britain in the early 1860s. Thus, football language – loosely defined as the elements making up football-related communication (spoken and written) at various levels, on and off the pitch – was, to begin with, synonymous with English football language, later to be converted to other varieties along with the international spread of the game, where English loans played a substantial role. [4] Further, due to the fast-rising popularity of the game from the late 19th century onwards, football language as a special language, with a vocabulary of its own, gradually came to infiltrate general language, continuously blurring and modifying the boundary between them.² For example, as an indication of this state of affairs, some familiarity with football language, even among those not directly involved in the game as players or spectators, was becoming increasingly common in the first few decades of the 20th century, not least in Britain. [5]

In the present context, the relatively condensed history of English football language may be seen as an advantage, in that there should be comparatively few completely dark linguistic corners. Further, given the brief time span of the modern game, the influence of historical and social change on its vocabulary over the past hundred years or so should be comparatively straightforward to trace. In many ways, today's football language can be viewed as a mirror not only of technical, tactical and organizational changes in or around the game, but also – in some layers of its vocabulary – of changes in society at large, whether of a political, financial or sociocultural nature. For instance, from an international perspective, the language policies of dictatorial regimes – and not only those – in 20th-century Europe often implied purist attitudes towards foreign loanwords, not least football terms, giving rise to the replacement of early English direct loans by loan translations or more independent indigenous creations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Such wider sociolinguistic issues, however, are not relevant to the present context. Our study of English football vocabulary will stick to the home turf of football language, being a diachronic, lexicological and lexicographic investigation of a sample of English football words and their spread into general language. In many cases, it may be expected, there should be a fairly transparent causal and temporal relationship between the first occurrence of a new term in the language, and its subsequent

acceptance by language users, and the underlying cause or “event” – e.g. a rule change or tactical innovation – that prompted it. Obviously, there was no need for terms like crossbar, penalty line and centre circle before the crossbar, penalty line and centre circle were introduced in the 1880s; similarly, the term goal net would have to wait until 1892 to make its first appearance. Other words or phrases may be more difficult to pinpoint as to their first occurrence, especially such terms as have resulted from more gradual changes of, say, a technical or tactical nature. When, for example, did expressions like one-two, through ball, offside trap and keep a clean sheet first turn up? Or ball watching and holding midfielder? In general, for dating of first occurrences, the Oxford English Dictionary (OED) is an indispensable tool, even though some very special football expressions may elude even this outstanding reference work, at least for a while.

As will already have appeared, however, first occurrences are not the only, perhaps not even the most intriguing, historical aspect of football language; nor is it the main concern of this study, aimed at illuminating the special–general language interface of English football vocabulary. It should thus be of interest to determine, as far as possible, when a certain term may be said to have become part of general language – and, possibly, how long it took after its first recorded occurrence. For example, when may football terms like free kick and penalty, or striker and yellow card, be said to have “entered” general language? And why did some terms take longer than others?

CONCLUSION

It is shown that, over the past hundred years, football vocabulary has gradually, at an accelerating pace, become more mainstream, as demonstrated by the growth of such vocabulary (e.g. striker, yellow card) in subsequent dictionary editions. Yet, some football terms make an esoteric impression, e.g. nutmeg ‘play the ball through the opponent’s legs’. Interestingly, such words also tend to be included in present-day dictionaries. Thus, football language is in a state of constant flux, responding to developments in and around the game. This is reflected in the dictionaries studied. In conclusion, due to the status and media coverage of the “people’s game” today, English general-purpose dictionaries have increasingly come to recognize much of its vocabulary as part of general language.

Needless to say, answers to such seemingly simple questions can never be an exact science. For one thing, general language is not a well-defined entity; nor, indeed is special language. In particular, the underlying problem

concerns how to devise and design a method to make the somewhat woolly notion of general language accessible to empirical investigation in more concrete, operational terms. What does it mean to say that a football word like free kick or striker is, or has become, part of general language? On what grounds, except purely intuitive or impressionistic, can such a claim plausibly be made? More specifically, what manageable criterion may be applied for a football word, whether of old or more recent provenance, of an exclusively football-specific or a more general sporting nature, to be considered part of general language? This basic question, among others, will be further discussed.

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